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SERVICE DESIGN FOR PRODUCT-SERVICE SYSTEMS USING CONTEXT-BASED ACTIVITY MODELING

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ABSTRACT

The integrated design capability for people-centered value is essential in industry competitiveness as well as in people's living. Here, integrated design stands for systematically integrated planning, concept design and realization design reflecting diverse viewpoints. Recently, the value creation paradigm in industry is shifting toward value creation through Product-Service Systems (PSS) where product and service elements are tightly integrated as systems. Ideally, in PSS, service issues should be dominant rather than product issues. The key in PSS design would be designing activities of various stakeholders considering interaction with other stakeholders as well as products. In this paper, a systematic methodology for designing services using context-based activity modeling method is presented together with examples of new activity designs,

Keywords: Service Design, Activity Design, Context-Based Activity Modeling, Product-Service Systems

INTRODUCTION

The integrated design capability for people-centered value is essential in industry competitiveness as well as in people's living. Here, integrated design stands for systematically integrated planning, concept design and realization design reflecting diverse viewpoints. Recently, the value creation paradigm in industry is shifting toward value creation through Product-Service Systems (PSS) where product and service elements are tightly integrated as systems. The term, i.e., specific concept, of PSS has firstly been introduced by Goedkoop et al. to consider ecological and economic issues simultaneously, and

they defined PSS as a marketable set of products and services, jointly capable of fulfilling a user's need [1]. They also addressed several strengths of PSS including value creation with quality and comfort, customizing and delivery of the offer to clients, cost reduction in initial investment by sharing, leasing and hiring, lower environmental load, and so forth. Mont also defined PSS as a system of products, services, supporting networks and infrastructure that is designed to satisfy customer needs and have a lower environmental impact than traditional business models [2][3]. In addition, other definition on PSS was proposed by Manzini as an integrated body of products and services and communication strategies that was conceived, developed and promoted by (a network of) actors to generate values for society [4]. A new PSS can be designed starting from an existing product of a manufacturing company by integrating service elements and product elements and by identifying new directions for business models.

Ideally, in PSS, service issues should lead product issues, and this is in a way natural as solutions for value provision function may have many different forms of realization with alternative products and services elements. That is, services are now dominant as products and technologies are rather saturated unlike the old days when goods dominated due to their rarity and novelty. Thus the key in PSS design would be designing activities of various stakeholders considering interaction with other stakeholders as well as products. Orchestrating activities of diverse stakeholders and defining and realizing PSS functions and structures would require systematic design methodologies and tools as well as creative design reasoning capabilities. In this paper, a systematic methodology for designing services

using context-based activity modeling method is presented together with examples of new activity designs.

PSS DESIGN METHOD

The PSS design method developed by the authors is composed of 6 phases such as (1) Requirement Identification and Value Targeting, (2) Stakeholder Activity Design, (3) PSS Function Modeling, (4) Function-Activity Mapping and PSS Concept Generation, (5) PSS Concept Detailing and (6) PSS Concept Prototyping. Detailed description of the PSS design process can be found in [8].

ECONOMICAL, ECOLOGICAL AND EXPERIENCE VALUE CONCEPT

To design PSS from a product, requirements, needs and values of various stakeholders of a product are identified and analyzed. To extract and address potential requirements of associated stakeholders, the life-cycle step analysis is conducted. These requirements are classified with the E3 values composed of economical, ecological and experience aspects [10].

While economical and ecological values have been introduced in [1], experience values are of primary interest as use experiences are the key driver for user-centered paradigm of industry. Experience values are classified into extrinsic and intrinsic at the first level. Extrinsic value is classified into functional and social value again. For the case of social value, in addition to the extrinsic social value such as status or connectivity, intrinsic dimension such as respect and spirituality seems to be applicable in PSS design as well. Intrinsic value includes emotional, social, and epistemic value. Emotional value is classified into active and reactive emotional values adopting Holbrook's framework for consumer values [11]. A detailed explanation of the experience values can be found in [16].

CONTEXT-BASED ACTIVITY MODELING AND DESIGN

Designing activities of various stakeholders reflecting design strategies formed using value proposition is a critical process in PSS design. Interactions between

service providers and receivers are designed through association of their activities. For this, service blueprint originally proposed by Shostack [12] is used. Each activity is detailed by reflecting its various contexts. To appropriately describe activities in more detail, the context-based activity modeling is proposed and described in detail in the next section.

PSS FUNCTION MODELING

Functions of PSS as well as its product elements and service elements are specified in top-down hierarchical manner. Adopting function-based design approaches of products, we have defined representation of PSS functions by including service receivers and providers [13]. While function-based design approaches considering functions, behaviors and structures are used in PSS design, combining these with stakeholder activities specifically is a critical aspect of PSS design, and this present challenges.

MODIFIED SERVICE BLUEPRINT

The modified service blueprint method was proposed [8] by inserting the layer of function between customer activity layer and on-stage service provider activity layer of service blueprint. The layer of function can represent the interactions among stakeholders. With the modified service blueprint, alternative PSS concepts can be compared by mapping different activities conducted by different stakeholders to realize same functions.

CONTEXT-BASED ACTIVITY MODELING AND ACTIVITY DESIGN

Activity is described in detail using the context-based activity modeling method and its schematic diagram is given in Figure 1. The core part of the activity description is the *action* verb. The *object* is the object of the action and is typically a PSS, which could be products, services or their combinations. Thus the object has function, behavior and structure parts as they constitute the base for all PSSs [7]. The activity is performed by the *active actor*, who is the subject stakeholder of the activity. In some cases, activity may have *passive actor* and/or *third-party actor* as well. For example, an activity description

that “the active actor threw a ball to the passive actor” includes the passive actor in addition to the active actor and the object. The *tool* is a PSS that is used in the action.

Figure 1. Context-Based Activity Modeling

Note that all the actors are stakeholders or users. Various characteristics of stakeholders such as static and dynamic properties as well as assessment are attached in representing stakeholders as in the case of typical user models. Static properties may include cognitive characteristics and physical properties, and dynamic properties may include states such as emotional orientation. Assessment could include understanding of the knowledge level of the stakeholder. Actor information is created and maintained through a stakeholder modeling method. The *environment* field of the activity model described the overall environment characteristics. InDoor, OutDoor or Virtual could make a basic class. The *event* of the activity points to another activity which motivates the current activity. The activity description is detailed using the *context* field. Mimicking the context category of ISO 20282-1 [14], the context is described by the *goal* context, the *relevant structures*, the *physical context*, and *psychological context*. The relevant structures include structural entities of various PSSs including products and services related with the activity. Physical context includes location, time, weather, lighting, sound etc. Psychological context includes affective and social context such as emotion, mood and crowdedness. Overall the activity is described such that the active actor does the action on the

object using the tool to the passive actor in the environment with motivation of the event under the context composed of goal, relevant structure, physical and psychological aspects. Note that the context-based activity modeling uses similar elements concept used in the scenario elements in [15].

As an illustrative example of the activity modeling, a specific case is shown in Figure 2. The active actor, who has never used a ticket vending machine before and with poor eye sight, purchases a train ticket using the vending machine in an outdoor train station in the suburb of London on a clear and sunny afternoon when there are many people crowded around the vending machine with hurried and worried mind condition.

Figure 2. Context-Based Activity Modeling Example

CASE STUDY: ACTIVITY DESIGN IN USED CLOTHES TAKEIN PSS

As an illustrative example of the activity design using the context-based activity modeling, we describe the design case of Clothes TakeIN PSS. *TakeIN* is the PSS series name for the effort to develop PSS that provide methods for desirable reuse of products, indicating *taking* them back *in* use rather than throwing away.

CLOTHES TAKEIN PSS IN CONVENIENCE STORES

For the life-cycle-step of reuse of clothes, there exist products such as used clothes bins located in shabby corners of back alley streets in town. Consider the activities of stakeholders involved in these bins. On a rainy night, would you feel happy to go out to donate your clothes into a bin located in a secluded corner of the back alley? Sometimes, you could find stray cats coming out such bins. The scenario of such experiences in used clothes donation is depicted in Figure 3. Negative reactive emotional experience values obtained from the bins in such physical contexts would reduce your active emotional experience value needed for your voluntary donating of clothes. Those clothes collected from such bins are then processed just like trashes and some useful clothes are selected by laborious efforts of human operators. Identifying those negative value attributes encountered in the current clothes bins, design strategies are thus set to convert those negative experience values into positive ones.

The key point in service design is designing the activities of various stakeholders that provide such desired values. Using the activity representation based on the context, the activity for a housewife donator, for example, to approach the clothes bin with the goal to donate used clothes can be described with the physical context information such that the weather is rainy and that the location of the

bin is in a secluded corner of the back alley, and with the psychological context such that the donator feeling unsafe and unpleasant. Under these contexts, the donation activity cannot provide positive experience values. But by replacing various elements of those contexts, rather positive experience could be achieved.

Now consider the physical context of the donator activities. The locations of used clothes bins would require proper accessibility of donators as well as proper accessibility of collectors using vehicles to pick up those collected clothes. While satisfying these requirements of the location context, the used clothes bins could be located inside of convenience stores. Convenience stores in countries like Korea, Japan, Taiwan and Hong Kong are very well distributed at locations to ensure good accesses both from donators and collectors with very friendly atmosphere to attract customers as shown in Figure 4. By replacing the location context from the shabby areas in back alley streets to the inside of convenience stores, a new PSS concept for used clothes reuse that drastically improve experience values of donators is to be designed. By changing the physical contexts of the activity of used clothes donation, totally different experiences and activities/behaviors of donators are to be designed. Donators' experiences and behaviors as if they gave presents to their nephews, for example, by giving the used clothes of their sons would be enabled. They even would like to provide further services like

Figure 3. Scenario of the Current Used Clothes Reuse.

packaging, repairing and cleaning used clothes as presents. Such a scenario of used clothes TakeIN PSS is depicted in Figure 5.

In designing such PSSs, our proposed modified service blueprints play important roles in associating PSS functions and activities of stakeholders. The functions and activities of the current used clothes bins located in back alley streets are shown in Fig. 6(a). A new PSS concept with more functions such as repairing and cleaning services added and carried out

by used clothes reuse service operating company or their suppliers is shown in Fig. 6(b). Yet another new PSS concept where donators are conducting those services themselves is shown in Fig. 6(c). Note that the used clothes TakeIN PSS station needs to be designed to enable desirable packaging experiences of donators. In this way new activities are designed. Using the PSS design methodology described in this paper, we designed the whole used clothes TakeIN PSS including the station and filed a patent for them

Figure 4. Location Context Change: Shabby Corner of Back Alley => Convenience Stores

Figure 5. Scenario of a New Used Clothes TakeIN PSS

Figure 6. Modified Service Blueprints for Used Clothes TakeIN PSS

CLOTHES TAKEIN PSS IN FASHION OUTLET STORES

Now by changing the location context to the inside of fashion outlet stores while keeping most of the functions of the Clothes TakeIN PSS station remain the same, yet another PSS is designed as shown in Figure 7. By introducing the Clothes TakeIN PSS in outlet stores, new flows of values are created. Earlier, with customers buying clothes in the stores, monetary values are added to the fashion brand. Now with the Clothes TakeIN PSS, customers bring used clothes to the PSS and may receive points to be used in purchase of other new clothes in the store. While the clothes are donated to beneficiaries through the brand, the brand obtained positive reputation for social effort. Also, with the Clothes TakeIN, customers actually give visits to the store. These visits would have not been made otherwise. Also continued relationship between customers and stores with information about customers can be accumulated. These new value attributes would turn into economic values for the fashion brand. A more detailed discussion on the business model aspect of PSS design can be found in [17]

CONCLUSION

In this paper, a systematic design method for service design for PSS using context-based activity modeling

has been introduced. As services aspect would be dominating, an activity design method with rich consideration of various context issues is important. Those activities of various stakeholders would need to be well associated with PSS functions. The authors' group has designed a number of PSSs using their PSS design method. One such case on used clothes reuse has been introduced in this paper as an illustrative example for the PSS design method by utilizing an aspect of physical context of the key activities using the context-based activity modeling. Note that the activity modeling enriches description of activities including association of subjective issues like various value themes as well as objective issues like physical conditions. By changing specific context items and related changes in other context items, different activities are designed in a systematic way. Also by changing actors of activities, as in the case of the active actor of packaging in the example in this paper, new activities and new services are designed. As activities are the key in service design, the proposed context-based activity modeling can play a central role in systematic designing of services and PSSs. A suite of design support software tools for various steps of PSS design, including ontology-based activity modeling, are currently being developed at the PSS Design Consortium group where design consulting companies and software development companies as well as a few university research teams are participating.

Figure 7. Location Context Change: Shabby Corner of Back Alley => Fashion Outlet Stores

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